

Sustain Sahel

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Table of Contents

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
2. SOIL PARAMETERS IMPLEMENTED IN THE PROJECT, RESULTS OF TREE/SHRUB IMPACT ON SOIL PROPERTIES	4
2.2. Chemical indicators	5
2.2.1 Impacts of shrub densities on main soil chemical parameters	5
2.2.2 Carbon stocks	7
2.2.1 Phosphorus, pH.....	8
2.2.2 Impact of shrub densities on soil exchangeable cations	8
2.3. Physical indicators	9
2.3.1 Texture.....	9
2.3.2 Structure: porosity, bulk density.....	10
2.3.3 Water retention/infiltrability.....	11
2.4. Soil Biological indicators	17
2.4.1 Faunal assessments using TSBF method.....	17
2.4.2 Microbial indicators.....	20
2.5. Indicators from the Biofuntool® toolkit.....	21
2.5.1 Carbon turnover indicators	22
2.5.2 Soil structure indicators	24
2.6. Validation of IR spectroscopy as a scaling up platform for analyzing the impact of cropping system on soil properties.....	24
2.6.1 Methodology outline	24
2.6.1 Spectral database and calibration samples selection	25
2.6.1 Predictions and future developments	25
2.6. Main conclusions	29
3. DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES RELATED WITH THE DELIVERABLE	30
Peer-reviewed publications.....	30
Submitted Papers	30
Communications in conferences	30
Outreach.....	32
4. REFERENCES	33

I. Executive summary

This deliverable reports on the use and implementation of the different soil quality indicators mobilized in SustainSahel to determine soil quality status, and the influence of ligneous species management on this status. As the project is still running and sample and data acquisition is ongoing with new field experiments planned for the 2024 cropping season, some of the soil studies will be extended and completed within the next year. The objective of this deliverable is to synthesize the relevant information this data provides across sites on links between practices, soil properties, and soil health. Here we illustrate with concrete examples the methodology and results of the interventions performed on soil characteristics within the SustainSahel project.

The analyses conducted so far:

- confirm the stimulatory impact of trees on a variety of soil parameters (physical, chemical and biological), but we find the size of this effect is largely soil type-dependent within the project area and also management-dependent
 - have involved collection and analysis of >1600 soil spectral data, of which 10% of the samples was used in calibration, and confirm suitability of IR-spectral approach to give estimates of key parameters such as C and N contents. Other parameters show promising correlations, but will need further calibration work
 - point out the importance of trees and tree residues impacts on water infiltration and dynamics, which is a key point in the water limited context of the region
 - provide a first assessment of Biofunctool parameters suitability to evaluate soil functionality and health in the area
- Altogether these sets of results validate the approach adopted in the SustainSahel project to provide a comprehensive toolkit of approaches to assess crop/shrub/tree/livestock systems impacts on soil properties.

2. Soil parameters investigated in the project and results of tree/shrub impact on soil properties

WP4-managed trials set up during the 2021/2022/2023 crop seasons were used for soil sampling for analysis of classical parameters (organic matter, physicochemical properties). In Senegal, this sampling was performed by ISRA who conducted supervision of the trials in Ouarkhokh, Niakhar and Tambacounda and IRD, which manages the analysis platform in Dakar. In Mali, this was conducted by IER in Sikasso and IPR in Koulikoro, and in Burkina Faso, by UNB on Yilou site/Kamboinse station and by INERA on Saria site.

Kamboinse site near Ouagadougou is an addition to the original proposed sites and serves as experimental station-counterpart of the Yilou site (farmer fields). In Kamboinse, the long-term Crop-NEWS trial was set up in 2012 by CIRAD to investigate the density and management impact of *Piliostigma reticulatum* on soil quality and crop productivity. This experiment provides an excellent platform for investigating the long-term interactions in *Piliostigma reticulatum* dominated Sahelian landscapes, in a controlled manner, and in safe conditions. Some trials on mulching *Piliostigma reticulatum* residues on fields were also conducted on the Gampela site close to Ouagadougou by IRD and University of Ouagadougou, in the same logic.

The number of samples collected during these campaigns is considerable: given the number of trials, conditions tested and repeats under WP4, this amounts to around 3000 samples in total.

In addition to this vast sampling activity, soil biological, structural and water dynamics-related parameters have also been recorded on several trials sites. Such parameters are more labour-intensive and cannot be conducted on every plot, but in selected situations, they give additional information on soil process functioning which are essential to better understand the observations collected in the whole network.

This combination of approaches gives us a view of correlation between tree/shrub insertion in cropping system and a whole range of soil properties on a large scale, which are connected and ultimately relying on biological stimulation of soil functions by ligneous species presence. It is worth noting that this data collection continues to be enriched

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

in 2024, as several trials are still under operation (and hopefully will continue being monitored beyond the project). But the amount of data collected so far is already informative enough to give consistent lessons on tree/shrub influence on soil properties in the area, with an unprecedented conjunction of efforts and data.

2.2. Chemical indicators

2.2.1 Impacts of shrub densities on main soil chemical parameters

Table I depicts a complete set of chemical analyses performed on Yilou area in Kamboinse experimental station as an example of the set of analyses we conducted during the project.

Figure 1 Design and view of Kamboinse experimental setup. Z = zai; SD = direct seeding; numbers = shrub densities

In this experiment, as seen in table I, under zai (local name for deep hole seeding), significant effects of shrub density were essentially recorded, on 0-10 cm depth samples, on C, N, P, and available K contents. In all these cases, the treatment with high shrub density (2000 stands/ha) gave significantly higher values than the others. For 10-20 cm depth, only differences in P content gave significant differences, although averages were quite close, in a manner which did not appear proportional to shrub density.

Under direct (no tillage) seeding + sorghum straw mulching few differences occurred for the upper 0-10 cm layer, only total soil P content exhibited some statistically significant variation with cropping system at 500 shrubs/ha giving higher values than at 2000 shrubs/ha). Note that SD2 (fallow) cannot be directly compared here because soil conditions are a bit different there. For the 10-20 cm layer, C, N, P, K and available K were significantly higher under high shrub density than under low shrub density ($P < 0,05$).

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Table I: Variation of major soil chemical parameters in function of shrub densities, under zai and under direct seeding

Profondeur (cm)	Traitements	pH -eau	pH -KCl	C-org (g.kg ⁻¹)	N-total (g.kg ⁻¹)	P-total (mg / kg)	K-total (mg / kg)	P -ass (mg / kg)	K-dispo (mg / kg)
0-10	Z – 0	6,10 ± 0,26	5,28 ± 0,22	4,57 ± 0,40 ^a	0,46 ± 0,03 ^a	66,77 ± 2,05 ^a	742,17 ± 38,42	2,22 ± 0,36	62,65 ± 11,43 ^a
	Z – 500	6,34 ± 0,21	5,54 ± 0,13	4,65 ± 0,70 ^a	0,48 ± 0,03 ^a	69,13 ± 6,45 ^a	827,67 ± 75,02	2,10 ± 0,17	83,86 ± 6,11 ^b
	Z – 1000	6,44 ± 0,06	5,77 ± 0,10	4,82 ± 0,90 ^a	0,48 ± 0,02 ^a	70,58 ± 1,49 ^{ab}	717,83 ± 73,13	2,24 ± 0,19	89,28 ± 9,65 ^b
	Z – 2000	6,35 ± 0,01	5,82 ± 0,14	6,67 ± 0,40 ^b	0,60 ± 0,03 ^b	101,14 ± 3,57 ^b	652,01 ± 121,01	2,66 ± 0,27	137,13 ± 16,48 ^c
	Probabilité	0,595	0,109	0,000	0,007	0,000	0,468	0,462	0,002
	Signification	NS	NS	THS	HS	THS	NS	NS	HS
	SD – 500	7,04 ± 0,37	6,20 ± 0,41	4,84 ± 0,50	0,48 ± 0,04	100,54 ± 13,61 ^c	917,36 ± 48,28	2,79 ± 0,79	116,91 ± 16,91
	SD ₁ – 2000	6,47 ± 0,10	5,77 ± 0,05	4,84 ± 0,79	0,49 ± 0,03	84,21 ± 6,61 ^b	889,05 ± 56,22	2,12 ± 0,56	125,29 ± 10,82
SD ₂ – 2000	6,66 ± 0,14	6,10 ± 0,15	4,97 ± 0,69	0,51 ± 0,04	61,01 ± 1,99 ^a	586,40 ± 16,85	3,47 ± 0,42	96,77 ± 19,89	
Probabilité	0,2760	0,495	0,736	0,963	0,035	0,201	0,437	0,601	
Signification	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS	
10 - 20	Z – 0	6,09 ± 0,04	4,88 ± 0,27	3,28 ± 0,25	0,33 ± 0,02	88,90 ± 2,51 ^c	908,62 ± 62,44	1,98 ± 0,25	72,02 ± 13,44
	Z – 500	6,03 ± 0,11	5,20 ± 0,12	3,95 ± 0,50	0,42 ± 0,02	74,37 ± 1,79 ^a	908,27 ± 77,24	2,46 ± 0,43	60,18 ± 10,97
	Z – 1000	6,20 ± 0,06	5,89 ± 0,57	3,93 ± 0,13	0,39 ± 0,02	90,04 ± 2,71 ^c	842,24 ± 66,03	2,54 ± 0,75	78,93 ± 13,72
	Z – 2000	6,21 ± 0,10	5,23 ± 0,06	3,87 ± 0,47	0,37 ± 0,04	83,03 ± 2,90 ^b	974,14 ± 63,70	1,96 ± 0,18	81,89 ± 19,16
	Probabilité	0,848	0,211	0,504	0,127	0,003	0,513	0,720	0,732
	Signification	NS	NS	NS	NS	S	NS	NS	NS
	SD – 500	6,12 ± 0,11	5,49 ± 0,36	3,07 ± 0,40 ^a	0,30 ± 0,01 ^a	72,02 ± 0,37 ^b	855,65 ± 26,97 ^b	2,50 ± 0,66	59,85 ± 6,51 ^a
	SD ₁ – 2000	6,12 ± 0,07	5,07 ± 0,16	4,52 ± 0,40 ^c	0,43 ± 0,03 ^c	85,37 ± 0,69 ^c	1161,51 ± 68,32 ^c	1,97 ± 0,13	80,90 ± 3,12 ^b
SD ₂ – 2000	6,31 ± 0,04	5,33 ± 0,17	3,94 ± 0,40 ^b	0,40 ± 0,05 ^b	49,70 ± 0,49 ^b	742,47 ± 70,77 ^a	2,55 ± 0,18	120,36 ± 5,22 ^c	
Probabilité	0,300	0,517	0,011	0,013	< 0,0001	0,048	0,601	0,0001	
Signification	NS	NS	S	S	THS	S	NS	THS	

Z= zai; SD = direct seeding; SD₁ = direct seeding high shrub density; SD₂= fallow, values 0, 500, 1000 et 2000 correspond to number of shrubs / ha of *Piliostigma reticulatum* (DC) Hochst. ± indicate standard deviation. When effect of treatment is significant on a parameter, different letters indicate significant differences between means (threshold 5%). NS: non-significant; S: significant, HS: highly significant, THS: very highly significant

2.2.2 Carbon stocks

Carbon and nitrogen contents are key central parameters of soil chemical properties, which are directly related to organic content.

Impact of shrub densities on organic carbon stock in soils

When combining soil C contents with soil bulk densities, it is possible to calculate the C stock in soil layers, as reported in figure 2, on a per ha basis. Our results show the trend in enhancement of carbon stocks under shrub density increase. Besides the beneficial effect on soil properties, this indicator is also useful in qualifying C balance of agricultural practices, especially in a context of global search for atmospheric C mitigation pathways.

Figure 2: Variation of organic carbon stocks under zaï (a) and direct seeding (b): Z= zaï; SD, SD1 = direct seeding ; SD2= fallow, values 0, 500, 1000 and 2000 correspond to number of shrubs / ha of *Piliostigma reticulatum* (DC) Hochst. Bars indicate standard errors.

Carbon stocks on Yilou site – farmers' fields

In farmers' fields we confirmed the effect of increasing shrub density on soil C (see figure 3 below, with shrub density ranges gathered by closest values and given as numbers/ha) by analyzing C stocks in a large diversity of fields. Even if the situation is highly variable, a general trend of C stock increase under higher shrub densities is clearly visible. Interestingly this effect also depends on soil type: it is significant on chromic lixisol LC (the most frequent in the area) on epipetric lixisol LEp and on epipetric plinthosol PE, but not on endopetric lixisol Len. Increasing shrub density effects on each soil type are highlighted by the red arrows (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Soil C stock assessments performed in a set of farmers' fields in Yilou, with different soil types (chromic lixisol LC, on epipetric lixisol LEp, epipetric plinthosol PE, endopetric lixisol Len) and shrub densities (range indicated by numbers on x-axis labels). P: *Piliostigma reticulatum*, G: *Guiera senegalensis*, C: *Combretum micranthum* (letters combinations mean a species mix in the field).

2.2.1 Phosphorus, pH

Low pH levels and low phosphorus contents are often encountered in the region. Both of them can in some cases be improved by organic matter additions. We therefore have measured these parameters in some of our trials. In the Kamboinse setup record (Table 1) these parameters tended to increase under shrub densification, but differences were not significant. Generally, influence of trees on these parameters are highly variable and therefore difficult to assign.

2.2.2 Impact of shrub densities on soil exchangeable cations

As enrichment in exchangeable cations, notably Calcium is one of the expected effects of shrub presence, we also measured these components in the Kamboinse site. The results shown in table 2 are pretty well correlated with major elements analyses, as significant enrichment in Ca²⁺, K⁺ and sum of exchangeable cations (SBE) was observed in the 0-10 cm layer with increasing shrub densities in the zai cropping system (P < 0,05). Under direct seeding, significant figures were only observed in the 10-20 layer, where K⁺ increased while Na⁺ decreased when shrub density increased.

These effects therefore appeared very limited in this context.

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Depth (cm)	Treatments	Ca ²⁺ (cmolc.kg ⁻¹)	Mg ²⁺ (cmolc.kg ⁻¹)	K ⁺ (cmolc.kg ⁻¹)	Na ⁺ (cmolc.kg ⁻¹)	SBE (cmolc.kg ⁻¹)	
0-10	Z-0	2,36 ± 0,36 ^a	0,85 ± 0,13	0,16 ± 0,03 ^b	0,02 ± 0,01	3,38 ± 0,50 ^a	
	Z-500	3,06 ± 0,43 ^{ab}	1,03 ± 0,21	0,21 ± 0,02 ^b	0,04 ± 0,01	4,35 ± 0,66 ^{ab}	
	Z-1000	3,03 ± 0,24 ^{ab}	0,98 ± 0,05	0,23 ± 0,02 ^b	0,03 ± 0,01	4,27 ± 0,24 ^{ab}	
	Z-2000	4,52 ± 0,61 ^b	1,20 ± 0,21	0,35 ± 0,04 ^c	0,07 ± 0,03	6,14 ± 0,88 ^b	
	P	0,021	0,348	0,001	0,177	0,032	
	S	S	NS	HS	NS	S	
	SD-500	4,39 ± 1,16	1,46 ± 0,37	0,30 ± 0,07	0,03 ± 0,01	6,18 ± 1,59	
	SD1-2000	3,84 ± 0,29	1,00 ± 0,08	0,32 ± 0,03	0,03 ± 0,01	5,20 ± 0,40	
	SD2-2000	4,35 ± 0,80	1,67 ± 0,71	0,26 ± 0,02	0,05 ± 0,01	6,33 ± 1,51	
	P	0,881	0,665	0,571	0,688	0,839	
	S	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
	10-20	Z-0	2,94 ± 0,59	0,98 ± 0,18	0,18 ± 0,03	0,03 ± 0,01	4,13 ± 0,78
		Z-500	3,84 ± 0,43	1,19 ± 0,14	0,15 ± 0,03	0,04 ± 0,01	5,22 ± 0,58
		Z-1000	4,90 ± 0,69	1,15 ± 0,03	0,20 ± 0,04	0,05 ± 0,01	6,80 ± 1,11
Z-2000		4,04 ± 0,67	1,00 ± 0,12	0,21 ± 0,05	0,05 ± 0,01	5,30 ± 0,74	
P		0,268	0,536	0,740	0,469	0,640	
S		NS	NS	NS	NS	NS	
SD-500		3,68 ± 0,56	1,18 ± 0,24	0,15 ± 0,02 ^a	0,07 ± 0,00 ^b	5,09 ± 0,78	
SD1-2000		3,94 ± 0,23	1,08 ± 0,19	0,21 ± 0,01 ^a	0,04 ± 0,00 ^a	5,27 ± 0,40	
SD2-2000		4,41 ± 0,60	0,92 ± 0,21	0,31 ± 0,01 ^b	0,09 ± 0,00 ^c	5,74 ± 0,71	
P		0,691	0,671	0,003	0,001	0,899	
S	NS	NS	HS	HS	NS		

Table 2: Variation of exchangeable cation contents in function of shrub densities, under zai or direct seeding : Z= zai; SD, SD1 = direct seeding ;SD2= fallow, values 0, 500, 1000 et 2000 correspond to number of shrubs / ha of *Piliostigma reticulatum* (DC) Hochst. ± indicate standard errors. Significant differences between average values are indicated by different letters (threshold 5%). SBE: sum of exchangeable bases (cations).

2.3. Physical indicators

2.3.1 Texture

Texture (soil particles size distribution between clay, silt and sand materials) is a geochemical soil status which is essentially driven by geological substrate and therefore less dependent on biological activities. However, it is often hypothesized that dust trapping by trees or shrubs may result in local enhancement in fine elements (clays 0-2 µm and fine silts 2-20 µm) beneath their canopies. We tested this hypothesis in the Niakhar area under *Faidherbia* canopies in a large dataset for which this parameter was analysed in 120 samples and further predicted by IR spectroscopy (see chapter 2.6 for details of the procedure) on 640 samples which constitute the dataset used for plotting figure 4. We did not find any differences in clay contents at this scale, and only a faint (but not statistically significant) increase in fine silt proportion.

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Figure 4 Effect of *Faidherbia albida* on fine particles proportion in upper layers of soil (0-10 cm, 10-20 cm and 20-30 cm). HH = out of tree influence, SH = under tree canopy. Symbols represent means and bars are standard deviations

2.3.2 Structure: porosity, bulk density

Impacts of shrub densities on soil porosity and amount of coarse elements in soil

Soil porosity is a parameter that is highly dependent on organic matter, soil biological activity, root densities and therefore might change under tree influence. In Kamboinse station however, no significant differences between treatments were recorded on this parameter. Note that the soil there is quite rich in coarse elements, which complicates this kind of measurement.

Figure 5: Variation of soil porosity and proportion of coarse elements (EG) of soil with different shrub densities under zai (a) or direct seeding (b), on 0-10 layer : Z= zai; SD, SD1 = direct seeding ; SD2 = fallow, values 0, 500, 1000 et 2000 correspond to number of shrubs / ha of *Piliostigma reticulatum* (DC) Hochst. \pm indicate standard errors. Significant differences between average values are indicated by different letters (threshold 5%).

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Conversely, in IPR trial in Mali, effect of mulching with shrub prunings during 3 years at 2.5 t/ha, was significant on soil bulk density (g/cm³) and porosity (%) as depicted in table 3. Interestingly, all mulching treatments increased soil porosity and in consequence decreased bulk density.

Treatment	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	porosity (%)
Control (T1)	1,59 a	40,02 b
<i>P. reticulatum</i> (T2)	1,30 b	51,14 a
<i>G. senegalensis</i> (T3)	1,32 b	50,40 a
<i>G. sepium</i> (T4)	1,25 b	52,72 a
<i>P. reticulatum</i> + <i>G. senegalensis</i> + <i>G. sepium</i> (T8)	1,29 b	51,38 a
p-value	0,001	0,001
Significance	HS	HS
CV%	6,7	6,9

Table 3: Effect of mulching with shrub material on top layer bulk density and porosity. Significantly different values are indicated by different letters (p< 5%).

2.3.3 Water retention/infiltrability

The assessment of tree effects on water dynamics and underlying processes will be further developed in D5.3, but we think it is useful here to depict the indicators we applied to infer soil water regime, and the main results they showed.

Trees and shrubs can influence the soil water regime by 1) long term effects by changing soil properties such as water holding capacity through organic matter deposition and 2) short term effect by changing the water balance components: water uptake, preferential infiltration from stem flow, surface soil evaporation mitigation by shading, root hydraulic redistribution. We measured parameters related to these phenomena in order to characterize tree effect on soil water content, infiltration and retention.

Water retention properties in function of shrub presence were measured using the pressure plate method (in Burkina Faso and Senegal). Soil water profiles were recorded as well either using TDR probes (in Senegal), or gravimetric methods (Burkina Faso and Mali). Results converge in that, generally, combination of better infiltration and higher retention result in higher soil water content along the profile at proximity of tree (see example below figure 6 for *Faidherbia albida*).

Figure 6: Change in average soil moisture content (SWC) (%) with depth (m) outside and under the crown of *F. albida*.

Soil infiltration rates were measured with the Beerkan method illustrated below, which is light and easy to apply and is also used in the Biofunctool kit. In Senegal, we have also tested an automated Beerkan setup in order to intensify the data acquisition for more in-depth studies.

Figure 7: Photo of the material used in the classical Beerkan method (left), and automated setup tested in Senegal (right)

Results shown in figure 8 indicate a trend of slightly higher infiltration and saturated hydraulic conductivity (K_s) in plots closed to trees (Under Tree) but no significant differences in this very sandy site.

Figure 8: Saturated hydraulic conductivities measured in plots outside trees (OST) and under trees (UT) in Sob Faidherbia Flux site (W. Faye et al., EGU 2023)

In Burkina Faso, in Saria and Yilou sites, measurements of infiltration rates in the presence of *Piliostigma reticulatum*, *Guiera senegalensis*, or under ligneous material mulch, showed that infiltration enhancement vs control was more pronounced under mulch conditions. All these results are quite consistent; example illustrations are given under the “Biofunctool section”.

In Mali as well, we tested the effects of mulching prunings of *Guiera senegalensis* J. L. Gmel, *Piliostigma reticulatum* (DC.) Hochst and *Gliricidia sepium* Jacq. Walp (during 3 years at 2.5t/ha) on soil water infiltration rate. The lowest rate was recorded on the plot with no prunings (control) at 0.16 cm/min., and the highest on the plots with *Guiera senegalensis* prunings and *Gliricidia sepium* prunings at 0.22 cm/min. for both (figure 9).

Figure 9: Effect of mulching on soil infiltration rate. Témoïn=Control, Pr=Piliostigma, Gus=Guiera, Gs=Gliricidia

Correlation with water dynamics:

Differences in infiltration rates induced by tree presence of mulch treatment are expected to influence soil water dynamics during the season. As an example to illustrate this, in Mali, in the Koulikoro site, the effect of ligneous material mulch application on soil moisture content under sorghum crop has been assessed by classical gravimetric method (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Soil water content at 20 cm depth (left) or 40 cm depth (right) in control conditions (T1) or in the presence of mulch from *Piliostigma reticulatum* (Pr), *Guiera senegalensis* (Gus), *Gliricidia sepium* (Gs) or a combination of 3, at different days after sowing (JAS).

Very interestingly, lower-than-control water content in top horizon and higher-than-control in deep horizon in observed under mulch during the three first sampling dates, an effect which tends to vanish afterwards. This is perfectly coherent with a better infiltration under mulch in the beginning of the rainy season.

In a different context, the effect of a shea tree (*Vitellaria paradoxa*) agroforestry system on soil moisture and maize (*Zea mays*) production potential was tested in the Sudanian zone of Mali. The experiment was conducted in the Zoumanana-Diassa area, in the village of Nagnassoni (11.5200 N; 005.657 W, 351 m). We tested the combination of distance to tree and wind exposure on water profile evolution throughout the season.

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Figure 11: Soil moisture measurement across the rainy season with 4 tubes inserted to 1.60 m depth with the following characteristics: tube 1, installed at the edge of the shea tree crown/shoot and following the prevailing wind direction (Sens_V_LH); tube 2, installed at twice the radius of the crown/tree in the direction of the prevailing wind (Sens_V_HH);- tube 3, installed at the limit of the crown/tree crown of the shea tree and in the opposite wind direction (Sens_Opp_V_LH); tube 4, installed at twice the radius of the crown/shoot in the opposite direction to the wind (Sens_Opp_V_HH). Results at 10cm, 60cm and 1m depth are shown.

Measurements were taken twice a week from the time the tubes were installed until the corn was harvested. The water available to plants across the soil profile (i.e. every 10 cm to the maximum tube depth) was calculated as the difference between the soil water content measured at a given time across the profile and the soil water content at the wilting point.

The main results obtained from monitoring water profiles show that at the surface (10 cm depth), soil water content is variable and influenced by the rainfall regime. Soil water content in the opposite direction to the wind and at the tree crown boundary (Sens_Opp_V_LH) is fairly high until August, followed by rapid drying out from September onwards. On the other hand, soil water content is at its highest at the surface of the canopy and in the direction of the prevailing wind (Sens_V_LH_) in October, when maize completes its vegetative cycle. Soil water content decreases towards the end of the season, drying out more rapidly at the crown edge than at the surface (10 cm deep).

Interestingly, at depth (60 cm and +1m), the trend is for higher soil water content at the crown edge (under tree influence) than outside the crown. At the end of the season, water dries out more quickly outside the canopy than at the canopy edge at soil depth. These results further illustrate the effect of tree on preferential water infiltration and storage.

Correlation with crop leaf water potential

As an additional indicator of tree influence on water availability to crops, measurements of predawn leaf water potential were performed in experiments in Saria area (Figure 12). Indeed, predawn plant water potential equilibrates with soil water potential as a result of stomatal closure

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

during the night, and is therefore a close indicator of soil water status. Locally made hydraulic membrane pressure chambers were used for these measurements, as they are of low cost and do not need compressed gas logistics.

Measurements performed in Saria area (Burkina Faso) showed that presence of shrub (*Piliostigma* or *Guiera*) consistently increased water potential in nearby sorghum when compared to crop outside of any shrub influence (Control). Application of shrub prunings as mulch had similar effects. This again is in good agreement with previous observation of higher water contents in the area surrounding trees and shrubs.

Figure 12: Predawn leaf water potential (bar) measurements in sorghum crops out of influence of shrubs (Control) or under the presence of *P. reticulatum* or *G. senegalensis* shrub, with different management options (pruned, unpruned (mature), mulched).

Such effect of tree vicinity on millet predawn leaf water potential was also observed in the *Faidherbia* parklands of the Niakhar area. In the figure 13 below, extracted from Clermont-Dauphin et al. (BASE 2023 ref [1]) which gathers data from 68 plots scattered in 5 villages, we can see that predawn water potential is higher in millet plots close to the tree than in open areas, both at beginning of rainy season and at flowering stage (Figure 12 a, b). This translates into less water stress as illustrated by midday water potential (Figure 12 c,d) and this effect is particularly strong at the critical flowering stage. This is certainly one of the key determinants of the enhancement of grain and straw yields which is observed close to the tree in the vast majority of plots (Figure 12 e,f).

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Figure 13: Pairwise comparisons of the following variables measured in open and close-to-tree subplots of five villages of central Senegal: **a, b**. Predawn leaf water potential of millet before and after millet flowering respectively; **c, d**. midday leaf water potential of millet before and after millet flowering respectively; **e, f**. millet grain and straw yield respectively. In a, b, c, d, each point is average of four repetitions collected in 68 pairs of subplot. In e, f, each point is from a 8 m² sampling area located in the center part of each subplot.

2.4. Soil Biological indicators

2.4.1 Faunal assessments using TSBF method

In Burkina Faso and Senegal, soil faunal assessments were performed. For this, the Tropical Soil Biology and Fertility (TSBF) method of Anderson and Ingram (1989 ref [2]) was used. In each elemental plot, a 25 cm square monolith of soil was removed to a depth of 30 cm using a metal frame. In some places sequential excavations were made on layers 0-5, 5-10, 10-15, 15-20 and 20-30 cm to collect soil macrofauna in a depth-resolved manner. Individuals that could not be identified in the field were preserved in alcohol at 75 °C in hermetically sealed vials for identification in the laboratory.

In Saria site (Burkina Faso), we tested influence of shrub management on density and composition of soil macrofauna. Macrofauna density decreases significantly from the 0-10cm layer to the 20-30cm layer. In the 0-30cm soil layer, macrofauna density is significantly higher in the mulch of *P. reticulatum* and *G. senegalensis* biomass (T4) and *P. reticulatum* in RNA (T3), regardless of year. The effect of year was significant only in the 0-10cm layer (Table 3).

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Table 4. Density of macrofauna sampled in 2021 and 2022 in Saria site. Treatments with a letter in common in the same column are not significantly different at the $P < 0.05$ threshold of the Kruskal-Wallis test

	Répétitions (n)	0-10cm	10-20cm	20-30cm	0-30cm
Traitements 2021					
T0	12	09 ± 01 c	05 ± 01 c	02 ± 01 c	16 ± 03 c
T1	12	23 ± 0 b	11 ± 01 b	02 ± 01 c	36 ± 02 b
T2	12	21 ± 0 b	27 ± 0 a	04 ± 01 c	52 ± 01 a
T3	12	35 ± 02 a	14 ± 01 ab	08 ± 01 a	57 ± 04 a
T4	12	44 ± 0 a	13 ± 0 ab	10 ± 01 a	67 ± 02 a
P-value		0,001	0,012	0,005	0,032
Significativité		HS	S	S	S
2022					
T0	12	12 ± 0 b	08 ± 01 c	05 ± 0 b	25 ± 01 b
T1	12	27 ± 0 ab	11 ± 0 b	06 ± 02 c	44 ± 03 ab
T2	12	20 ± 01 b	15 ± 01 b	06 ± 01 c	41 ± 02 b
T3	12	51 ± 3 a	19 ± 03 a	11 ± 02 b	81 ± 08 a
T4	12	56 ± 01 a	17 ± 01 b	13 ± 01 a	86 ± 02 a
P-value		0,017	0,001	0,011	0,04
Significativité		S	HS	S	S
Effet année					
2021	60	54 ± 01 b	31 ± 0	26 ± 0	111 ± 1
2022	60	67 ± 0 a	53 ± 0	32 ± 01	152 ± 2
P-value		0,005	0,207	0,152	0,451
Significativité		S	NS	NS	NS

T0: Control with no shrubs; T1: *P. reticulatum* coppiced; T2: *G. senegalensis* coppiced; T3: *P. reticulatum* in farmer-managed natural regeneration (RNA); T4: Mulch of *P. reticulatum* and *G. senegalensis* biomass; S: Significant; NS: Not significant.

Influence of shrub management on soil macrofauna diversity

Macrofaunal diversity was significantly influenced by shrub management (T1, T2, T3, T4), where it was higher than in the shrub-free control (T0). Treatment T4, mulched with the biomass of *P. reticulatum* and *G. senegalensis*, stood out from the other treatments (Table 5)

Table 5 Diversity (H') and equitability (E) indices for sampled macrofauna. Treatments with a letter in common on the column are not significantly different at the $P < 0.05$ threshold of the Kruskal-Wallis test

Traitements	Répétitions (n)	2021		2022	
		H'	E	H'	E
T0	12	1,10 ± 0,33 b	0,45 ± 0,04 c	1,29 ± 0,37 b	0,49 ± 0,15 b
T1	12	1,69 ± 0,70 a	0,73 ± 0,24 ab	1,71 ± 0,40 a	0,85 ± 0,16 a
T2	12	1,73 ± 0,57 a	0,78 ± 0,21 ab	1,46 ± 0,24 ab	0,84 ± 0,12 a
T3	12	1,85 ± 0,85 a	0,85 ± 0,31 a	1,56 ± 0,45 ab	0,75 ± 0,16 a
T4	12	1,87 ± 0,56 a	0,83 ± 0,16 a	1,55 ± 0,49 ab	0,81 ± 0,14 a
p-value		0,041	0,021	0,011	0,045
Significativité		S	S	S	S

T0: Control with no shrubs; T1: *P. reticulatum* coppiced; T2: *G. senegalensis* coppiced; T3: *P. reticulatum* in RNA; T4: Mulch of *P. reticulatum* and *G. senegalensis* biomass; S: Significant; NS: Not significant.

This example of faunal assessment in the Saria area clearly shows the strong effect of mulching with ligneous material or of enhanced *Piliostigma* regeneration on insect densities.

In a different context, in the Niakhar area, around the Sob village, soil faunal assessments were conducted to analyse effect of *Faidherbia* tree presence under two contrasting field management types: home fields (champ de case, close to homesteads, receive annual input of organic manure) and outfields (champ de brousse, distant from the village, do not receive manure except from occasionally roaming livestock. (see map below and figure 14 results).

We again find that tree presence enhances both soil faunal abundance and diversity. Interestingly this effect is more marked in outfields, where tree-influenced soils exhibit the highest densities. This looks as if, and this was not really expected, the more intensive management and regular manuring which occurs in homefields, somehow dampened the amplitude of the specific tree effect.

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Figure 14: Soil faunal inventories performed either in homefields (close to the village, right side on photo, CC or “Champ de case” in legends) or in outfields (further from the village, left side on photo, CB or “Champ de brousse” in legends), and in each field either close to the tree (“Sous les arbres”) or far from trees (“Loin des arbres”). A: remote sensing view, B: Shannon diversity index, C,D : abundance and proportions, respectively, of main invertebrate groups.

2.4.2 Microbial indicators

In Senegal, soil samples have been collected for assessment of microbial (bacterial and fungal) communities associated with the presence of tree/shrub by soil DNA sequencing and metabarcoding. Samples have been frozen and are kept in order to perform assessments of bacterial and fungal communities with respect to shrub vicinity. The approaches will be the same that the ones we have recently developed and validated in the same region and same soils to quantify millet cultivar effect on rhizosphere communities [5].

In terms of interaction with fungi, besides identifying implied species, it is important to specifically assess the efficiency of mycorrhization of crops in the different systems, as it is supposed to be an important component of their resilience towards water and nutrient limitations. Studies at ISRA on combined effects of organic fertilization, cultivar effect and inoculation on mycorrhizal intensity in pearl millet, which have been conducted in controlled conditions (figure 15 and ref [6]), will be used as a basis to evaluate tree and shrub effects on these parameters on mycorrhization within the last cropping season in the project.

Figure 15: Effect of *G. mosseae* inoculation and organic fertilization on the intensity of mycorrhization in pearl millet varieties. T0, control; T1, *G. mosseae*; T2, cow dung; T3, horse manure; T4, *G. mosseae* + cow dung; and T5, *G. mosseae* + horse manure. The bars represent the standard deviations. For each variety, values with the same letter do not significantly differ ($p < 0.05$)

2.5. Indicators from the Biofuntool® toolkit

In several trials an innovative in-field assessment of ecological functioning (BIOFUNCTOOL®) was conducted as well (ref [3-4]). Depending on sites and opportunities, activities essentially concentrated in testing six indicators on the 9 described in the Biofuntool documentation. We used three indicators related to organic matter dynamics: POXC as a proxy of soil active C content, bait laminas as tests for meso/microfaunal activity (quite interesting to compared to faunal identification records), SituResp as a proxy for organic matter mineralization dynamics, and three parameters related to soil structure maintenance: visual estimation of soil structure (VESS test), aggregate stability in water, and Beerkan-measured water infiltration

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Figure 16: Illustration of tests from the biofunctool kit and their implementation in Burkina Faso with training of students from INERA, UNB and local technicians by IRD.

2.5.1 Carbon turnover indicators

In Saria site, we analyzed the impact of shrub management or ligneous mulch application on structure-related Biofunctool parameters. Analysis of results showed that labile C amount in soil and basal respiration were both affected by treatment, with higher values under shrub influence or mulch than in control. Amplitude of effect varied between the 2 years, notably for basal respiration (significant differences in 2022, not in 2021). Bait lamina consumption by soil fauna also showed some stimulation in shrub-influenced plots vs control, but difference was not significant.

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Table 6. Influence of shrub-based treatments on labile carbon (POXC), basal soil respiration and bait lamina substrate degradation rate by soil fauna.

Treatments	Labile C POXC (mg/kg sol)		Basal Respiration (Q.C02)		Substrate degradation (%/day)	
	2021	2022	2021	2022	2021	2022
T0	376,70 ± 152,64 b	406,42 ± 142,32 b	1,21 ± 0,68	0,73 ± 0,79 b	26,51 ± 17,68	69,86 ± 22,29
T1	560,06 ± 185,85 a	561,25 ± 143,40 a	1,18 ± 0,65	1,16 ± 0,50 a	33,48 ± 10,25	82,03 ± 15,39
T2	479,79 ± 272,66 ab	519,27 ± 156,33 ab	1,21 ± 0,70	1,22 ± 0,47 a	27,91 ± 9,86	78,68 ± 16,67
T3	484,06 ± 112,96 ab	552,24 ± 79,23 a	1,24 ± 0,68	1,27 ± 0,39 a	41,21 ± 1,55	84,60 ± 11,93
T4	475,94 ± 165,72 ab	560,83 ± 134,80 a	1,32 ± 0,61	1,08 ± 0,64 ab	31,59 ± 4,43	79,46 ± 17,31
p-value	p < 0,0001	p < 0,0001	0,824	p < 0,0001	0,525	0,623
Significance	HS	HS	NS	HS	NS	NS

T0 : Control ; **T1** : Coppiced *P. reticulatum* recépé ; **T2** : Coppiced *G. senegalensis*; **T3** : *P. reticulatum* Farmer-managed natural regeneration ; **T4** : Mulch with *P. reticulatum* et *G. senegalensis* biomass. HS : Highly significant ; NS : Non significant ;

In the Niakhar area in Senegal, we were interested in testing combined effects of tree vicinity and of tree management (pruning vs not pruning) on soil C indicators (Figure 17). The only significant effects were observed for POXC. A clear effect of tree vicinity which enhanced POXC was observed. Conversely, effect of pruning or not the tree did not bring a significant additional effect.

Figure 17: Soil labile carbon measured under (xNES, xES) and outside (xEH, xNEH) tree crown in 3 localities from the Niakhar area in Senegal. Different letters on bars indicate significantly ($p < 0.05$) different values.

2.5.2 Soil structure indicators

In Saria site in Burkina Faso, we found significant differences between treatments in terms of visual estimation of soil structure and of water infiltration rate, but not in terms of aggregate stability (Table 7: Soil structure indicators measured in Saria, Burkina Faso: VESS, aggregate stability, water infiltration, under different shrub management treatments.), with all parameters tending to be improved by shrub presence or shrub mulch when compared to control (the lower the better for VESS, the higher the better for the others).

Table 7: Soil structure indicators measured in Saria, Burkina Faso: VESS, aggregate stability, water infiltration, under different shrub management treatments.

Treatment	VESS (score/cm)	Ag. surface (0- 2cm)	Ag. sol (2- 10cm)	Infiltration rate (ml/mn)	
				2021	2023
T0	2,81 ± 0,44 a	5,05 ± 1,71	4,95 ± 1,76	68,47 ± 59,53 b	43,43 ± 36,13 b
T1	2,63 ± 0,32 ab	5,84 ± 0,69	6 ± 0	165,66 ± 102,32 a	642,59 ± 164,11 a
T2	2,53 ± 0,39 ab	5,63 ± 1,06	6 ± 0	96,07 ± 130,86 ab	157,90 ± 140,69 b
T3	2,75 ± 0,55 a	6 ± 0	6 ± 0	53,57 ± 32,53 b	134,88 ± 114,91 b
T4	2,31 ± 0,19 c	5,67 ± 0,71	6 ± 0	141,23 ± 166,69 ab	270,70 ± 199,55 ab
p-value	0,027	0,103	0,103	0,041	p < 0,0001
Significance	S	NS	NS	S	HS

T0 : Control ; **T1** : Coppiced *P. reticulatum*; **T2** : Coppiced *G. senegalensis*; **T3** : *P. reticulatum* Farmer-managed natural regeneration ; **T4** : Mulch with *P. reticulatum* et *G. senegalensis* biomass. HS : Highly significant ; NS : Non significant ; **VESS** : visual evaluation of soil structure

2.6. Validation of IR spectroscopy as a scaling up platform for analyzing the impact of cropping system on soil properties

2.6.1 Methodology outline

Given the number of samples, wet analysis of all chemical and physical parameters will not be feasible for the diversity of situations we wish to analyse. Therefore, all collected soils, after drying and sieving for conservation and standardization of condition, undergo spectroscopy in order to systematically collect Infrared (IR) data. An IR spectrometer specifically dedicated to this task has been bought in Burkina Faso and complements the devices already in place in Dakar.

IR spectroscopy allows to estimate wet chemical parameters such as C and N contents with virtually no operating costs, provided that a calibration database allowing correlation between spectral shape and parameter value is available.

2.6.1 Spectral database and calibration samples selection

As far as possible, all the plots of the trials which were set up during the SustainSahel cropping seasons were subjected to soil sampling. In Senegal, this sampling was performed by ISRA who conducted supervision of the trials in Ouarkhokh, Niakhar and Tambacounda and IRD, which manages the analysis platform in Dakar. In Mali, this was conducted by IER in Sikasso and IPR in Koulikoro, and in Burkina Faso, by UNB on Yilou site/Kamboinse station and by INERA on Saria site.

Given the number of samples, wet analysis of all chemical and physical parameters will not be feasible. Therefore, the strategy is to submit all collected soils, after drying and sieving for conservation, to IR spectrum analysis, and to analyze chemically only the subset which is needed to build the IR model (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Depiction of implementation of the process for IR spectrum analysis

The different steps of the strategy are depicted above: spectral data are acquired on all samples (actual set of 600 spectra here, top left). Then, a PCA-guided analysis of these spectra is used to select a subset of samples representing the diversity of spectral shapes (top right), after which selected samples are subjected to wet analysis, and a model is calibrated using these reference values to predict parameters of interest from spectral data (bottom left).

For IR spectroscopic analysis of Burkina Faso and Mali samples, the dedicated spectrometer broke down and data collection was interrupted. The apparatus is currently under repair in France, which delays the process and is planned to go back to Ouagadougou in July 2024.

2.6.1 Predictions and future developments

In Figure 19 we see the IR model prediction vs actually lab-measured parameter values for the 120 samples which were selected for IR approach calibration. It is interesting to notice that although sample selection was based purely on spectral data, these soil samples exhibit a diversity in C, N, fine particles, phosphorus and cation contents which is quite representative of the region, and gathers samples under trees, under shrub, and out of their influence. Model building is in progress, as correlations are good for some parameters (C, N, fine silts, Calcium for instance), but of insufficient precision for the others. But complementary analyses are going on, new calibration points have been selected and we expect consistent data from this approach to come in the near future even with less easy to predict parameters.

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Figure 19: IR spectral model calibration for textural and chemical parameters of soils sampled on the SustainSahel trials network in Senegal. 120 samples out of >1600 were analyzed by wet chemistry to give these calibration values.

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Figure 20: Average + standard deviation of soil C content prediction by IR outside tree (HH) or under tree (SH) in function of depth (in cm)

Once the models are calibrated, it becomes possible to predict parameters in the whole range of samples and use it to analyze specific effects of trees or shrubs depending on the type of cropping system we analyze. For instance, figure 20 which averages 310 data points from IR prediction of soil samples collected under or outside *Faidherbia* tree in a variety of situations in the Niakhar area, clearly indicates that C content is enhanced to a large extent in the upper horizons, but that effect tends to vanish with increasing depth. This validates the approach and gives an estimation of the large scale average effect that can be expected from large scale adoption of this agroforestry practice, even if still to be improved and refined by additional calibration points.

Figure 21: Average + standard deviation of soil C content prediction by IR under tree (SH) in function of depth (in cm) and in function of tree management practice: regularly pruned (E) or unpruned (NE)

This dataset allows us to test other hypotheses. For instance, it could be hypothesized that tree management (regularly pruning vs letting the tree unpruned) may have some differential impact on C content under the tree. Our records in the Niakhar area indicate that this is not the case for the Faidherbia system in this context (Figure 21).

2.6. Main conclusions

At this stage of the project, we were able to get data on the entire panel of parameters that we had planned to use in order to qualify soil status, and the influence of ligneous species management of introduction on soil parameters.

The analyses conducted so far confirm the stimulatory impact of trees on a variety of these soil parameters (physical, chemical and biological). By comparing situations, we find the amplitude of these effects are largely soil type-dependent within the project area, CSL system dependent and also management-dependent.

Based on the collection of >1600 soil spectral data and analysis of 10% of the samples for calibration, we confirm the suitability of IR-spectral approach to give estimates of key parameters such as C, N, Ca, fine particles contents on large numbers of samples in order to assess the diversity and spatial heterogeneity which is inherent to agroforestry systems. Other parameters show promising correlations, but will need further calibration work to be used for dedicated projections.

In all explored situations, and by various approaches, we point out the importance of trees and tree residuals impacts on water infiltration and dynamics, which is a key point in the water limited context of the region. Very consistently, trees and shrubs presence or mulch improved soil structure and porosity, which resulted in enhanced water infiltration. This effect, alongside with enhanced water retention properties due to improvement in C contents, induced improvement of water availability along soil profile. Interestingly, this enhancement of water conditions near the tree/shrub is visible at the level of water potential of the associated crop species, which certainly explains a significant part of the improvement in crops yields that is often observed in our setups.

Further, we have been able to develop a field based and low cost assessment of essential soil functions, using 6 out of 9 Biofunctool parameters to evaluate soil functionality and health in the area, and demonstrated the sensitivity of these parameters to tree and shrub influence.

Altogether this set of results validates the strategy conducted in the SustainSahel project to give a comprehensive toolkit of approaches to qualify CSL systems impacts on soil properties.

3. Dissemination activities related with the Deliverable

Peer-reviewed publications

Clermont-Dauphin C., N'Dienor M., Leroux L., Ba H.S., Bongers F., Jourdan C., Roupsard O., Do F.C., Cournac L., Seghier J.. 2023. *Faidherbia albida* trees form a natural buffer against millet water stress in agroforestry parklands in Senegal. *Biotechnologie, Agronomie, Société et Environnement*, 27 (3) : p. 182-195. DOI: [10.25518/1780-4507.20477](https://doi.org/10.25518/1780-4507.20477)

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Submitted Papers

Influence des modes de gestion de *Piliostigma reticulatum* (DC.) Hochst. et *Guiera senegalensis* J.F.Gmel. sur la macrofaune du sol en zone nord soudanienne du Burkina Faso Bazongo Bessibié, Clermont-Dauphin Cathy, Zallé Harouna, Hien Mipro, Yélémo Barthélémy

Les ligneux au champ en zone nord-soudanienne du Burkina Faso : Biodiversité, potentiel de production de la biomasse foliaire à l'échelle de la parcelle et perceptions paysannes Bessibié BAZONGO^{1,4*}, Cathy CLERMONT-DAUPHIN², Soumaïla GUIRE³, Mipro HIEN¹, Barthélémy YELEMOU⁴,

Communications in conferences

Influence des modes de gestion des arbustes *Piliostigma reticulatum* (DC.) Hochst. et *Guiera senegalensis* J.F.Gmel. sur la disponibilité de l'eau pour le sorgho dans les agrosystèmes familiaux en zone nord soudanienne du Burkina Faso. Colloque international Burkina Faso/Sénégal du 21 au 23 septembre 2022 Bessibié BAZONGO¹, Barthélémy YELEMOU², Cathy CLERMONT-DAUPHIN³, Mipro HIEN¹

Influence des modes de gestion des arbustes *Piliostigma reticulatum* (DC.) Hochst. et *Guiera senegalensis* J.F.Gmel. sur la mycorhization du sorgho en zone nord soudanienne du Burkina Faso. Conférence scientifique sur les mils : valorisation des mils pour une résilience à la crise sécuritaire et environnementale en Afrique de Ouest, 19 -21 décembre 2023, Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso. Bazongo Bessibié¹, Clermont-Dauphin Cathy², Hien Mipro¹ Yélémo Barthélémy³

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

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Posters

Gnissien, M., Coulibaly, K., Barro, M., Douzet, J. M., Cournac, L., Nacro, H. B. 2022. Effets longue-durée de différentes densités de *Piliostigma reticulatum* (DC) Hochst sur la dynamique du carbone et de l'eau en zone nord-soudanienne du Burkina Faso. Université Joseph KI-ZERBO, 1 p. Journées doctoriales, 16-18 février 2022, Ouagadougou (Burkina Faso).

Gnissien, M., Coulibaly, K., Barro, M., Douzet, J. M., Cournac, L., Cicek, H., Nacro, H. B. 2022. Long term effects of *Piliostigma reticulatum* (DC) Hochst' densities on carbon and water storage and dynamics of an epipetal Plinthosol in Burkina Faso's northern Sudanian area. Québec : Université de Laval, 1 p. World Congress on Agroforestry 2022. 5, 2022-07-17/2022-07-20, Québec (Canada).

Gnissien, M., Coulibaly, K., Traoré, M., Cournac, L., Nacro, H.B. Les parcs arbustifs sont-ils un moteur de gestion durable de la fertilité du sol en zone nord-soudanienne du Burkina Faso ? Conférence sur l'intensification écologique durable, 2024, 23-25 avril 2024, Dakar, Sénégal, 1p.

Influence des modes de gestion des arbustes sur la macrofaune du sol et la production du sorgho dans les agrosystèmes familiaux en zone nord soudannienne du Burkina Faso. Colloque scientifique en hommage au Professeur Sita GUINKO, Université Joseph KI-ZERBO, Ouagadougou, 20 – 22 septembre 2023 « Gestion durable de la biodiversité et changements environnementaux » Bessibié BAZONGOI, Cathy CLERMONT-DAUPHIN2, Mipro HIENI Barthélémy YELEMOU3

Deliverable 5.2. Soil chemical, spectral and functional indicators

Poster 2 : « Influence des modes de gestion des arbustes sur la quantité du carbone labile et la vitesse d'infiltration de l'eau dans les parcelles culture du sorgho en zone nord soudanienne du Burkina Faso ». 4^{ème} édition de la Conférence Intensification Durable Résiliences et adaptations des agricultures. Transition agroécologique et souveraineté alimentaire 23 au 25 Avril 2024 –CIGASS, UCAD- Dakar, Sénégal. Bessibié BAZONGOI, Cathy CLERMONT-DAUPHIN², Mipro HIENI Barthélémy YELEMOU³

Outreach

The main results from soil response to CSL systems are part of discussion with SustainSahel-implied farmers during innovation platforms meetings, in interaction with WP2 and WP4 contributions.

4. References

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